

Yellow Flower Hill (Huanghuagang) 72 Martyrs' Cemetery

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On April 27, 1911 (the twenty-ninth day of the third month according to the lunar calendar), a few Guangzhou residents were aroused before dawn. A group of local gentry, businessmen, overseas students, and secret society members armed with pistols and explosives smuggled from Hong Kong broke into the residence of the Viceroy of Guangdong and Guangxi, Zhang Mingqi (1875–1945). Some leaders of the insurgence had joined the Revolutionary Alliance founded by Sun Yat-sen in Japan in 1905. The skirmish lasted for just a day because the plot had already been leaked to the authorities. The revolt leaders were expecting the reinforcements led by Zhao Sheng (1881–1911) and Hu Hanmin (1879–1936) to join them, but they did not materialize. Many of the rebels were killed in battle. The Qing authorities captured and executed a number of others immediately afterwards. The body count was recorded at 86, but only 72 of the bodies could be identified. These 72 men became to be known as the Yellow Flower Hill martyrs. The site, with its simple graves, became the Yellow Flower Hill where a memorial complex was first constructed in the late 1910s. During the 1920s and 1930s, the Guangdong leadership renovated the tomb multiple times, adding new decorative structures and expanding the gravesite into an impressive monument that adorned the regionally circulated currency. The magnificent structure was built with marble, bricks, and stone, and adorned with eclectic elements, all of which marked a departure from features of traditional shrines. On the very top is the Statue of Liberty (Goddess of Liberty 自由女神) holding a book and a mallet, in honor of those who fought for Han Chinese people's freedom from the Manchu rulers. The statue was installed on top of a brick wall. The top of the main monument was adorned with decorative bricks inscribed with names of overseas Nationalist branches, which donated to the construction. The commemorative structure was used in regional coins in the 1920s and 1930s. Scattered through the complex were incense burner columns with Buddhist swastikas, iron-cast skulls as capitals, and the Nationalist Party blue-sky white-sun emblem. The site is a significant example of the cult of the dead in modern and contemporary China.

Date Range: 1911 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Huanghuagang

Region tags: China, Asia, East Asia

Guangzhou metropolitan area

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Ho, Virgil Kit Yiu. "Martyrs or Ghosts? A Short Cultural History of a Tomb in Revolutionary Canton, 1911-1970." *East Asian History* 27 (June 2004): 99-138.
- Source 2: Vu, Linh D. *Governing the Dead: Martyrs, Memorials, and Necro-citizenship in Modern China*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 2021. Chapter 1
- Source 3: Zou Lu 鄒魯, ed. *Huanghuagang qishier lieshi shilüe 黃花崗七十二烈士事 [The Yellow Flower Hill seventy-two martyrs' biographies]*. Unknown: Unknown, 1922.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: http://www.yuexiu.gov.cn/zjyx/yxjd/gzjdgms/content/post_8658148.html
- Source 1 Description: Introduction to the Huanghuagang site by the People's Government of Yuexiu District, Guangzhou, Guangdong

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 2007

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: There was a report of Eastern Han burials at the site and limited excavation was carried out around 2007.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

– Hill

Notes: The site has a slight elevation, hence the character 崗 (hill, mound) in the name.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Mound

– Plantings

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The site is located in Guangzhou (Canton), a highly urbanized, commercialized, and populous city.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Notes: The site when it was first constructed was outside the city's boundaries. However, today it is part of the urban area.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Purposefully placed plants

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The site was first built in 1912. During the Republican period, the tombs of martyrs were renovated multiple times in 1922, 1924, and 1934. New decorative structures were added to the old ones and the gravesite was expanded into an impressive monument in the middle of a large park by 1935.

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The structures have been built and renovated many times.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Memorial

Notes: During the Republican era, March 29 was considered the anniversary of the Yellow Flower Hill uprising. Various commemorative activities took place on that day.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

Notes: The Statue of Liberty was removed during the Cultural Revolution (1966-1976). It was later restored. Some damages to the tombstones and steles occurred during the Cultural Revolution are not restored.

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

Notes: According to Chinese media, there was a discovery of Eastern Han burials in 2007. But these are not part of the structure seen today.
(<https://tech.sina.com.cn/d/2007-11-16/11221856369.shtml>)

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: However, there is a Statue of Liberty on the top of the main building. In Chinese, it is called 自由女神 (Goddess of Freedom). 神 does imply a transcendent being. But in this case, it symbolizes the ideal of liberty. The Huanghuagang is not to worship the Goddess of Liberty, but to commemorate revolutionary martyrs.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Notes: However, it is to commemorate the revolutionary predecessors (革命先烈) of modern China. They can be understood as "non-divine ancestors."

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: It was built by supporters of the Republican revolution and of the Chinese Nationalist Party.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– War/battle

Notes: It was created after the Second Guangzhou Uprising in 1911.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: The site was built from donations from supporters of the Republican revolution and members of the Chinese Nationalist Party

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The largest structure is the monument to the 72 Yellow Flower Hill Martyrs. There are tombs of other martyrs that are smaller in size. There are also graves of lesser known people from the Republican era who wanted to be in close proximity of the revolutionary martyrs.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 10

Notes: The area is now a large park with mostly open space and plantings.

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 200

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 17

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 60

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 3

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood

– No

↳ Grass

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Granite

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

–Yes [specify]: Cement

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: There is a Goddess of Liberty statue.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Portraits of martyrs placed on their tombstones

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– No

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: There is a statue of the Goddess of Liberty.

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Busts of heads

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Reliefs depict the uprising in 1911 and the leadership of Sun Yat-sen in the Republican revolution.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: There are inscriptions that narrate the historical event, the circumstances of the martyrs' deaths, and the commemorative acts of the authorities.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: There is statue of Goddess of Liberty,

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: Buddhist swastika and the Blue Sky and White Sun symbol of the Chinese Nationalist Party

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: Statue of Liberty as a woman holding a torch.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Stone tablets with names of the dead

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– No

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– Yes

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: The martyrs were buried in a tomb on an elevation in order to benefit from the geomantic advantage in the landscape.

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Collective burial of those who were not identified after the 1911 uprising.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

Notes: On the main building, there are four characters 浩氣長存, which means “the spirits (of these martyrs) last for eternity.” It can be interpreted that the martyrs remain in the spirit form among the living. In the early twentieth century, the dead buried at the site were also perceived as ghosts that needed to be pacified with offerings.

Human spirits can be seen:

– No

Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: On the anniversary of the uprising, there is usually a large-scale commemorative event.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Groups and individuals visit the site and bring offerings such as flowers to pay respect to these martyrs. Descendants of martyrs who are buried at the site also visit.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Thousands

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Once a year

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– I don't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Notes: In the Republican era, wine might have been used during the ritual as it was customary to do so at the graves.

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Today, offerings are usually the form of flower wreaths specifically used in funerals.

Notes: In the Republican era, paper moneys were burnt as offerings.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

Notes: Students in the area are organized to visit the site as part of their school activities.

↳ By specific individuals

– No

Notes: However, leaders of the Chinese Nationalist Party in Taiwan sometimes visit the site and make offerings.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– I don't know

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The place is very well maintained.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Huanghuagang is considered one of the most sacred sites in the history of modern China, especially of the Chinese Nationalist Party. In the early 1910s, groups of soldiers and students had pilgrimages to the site. When the Party came to power in Guangzhou in 1925, it perpetuated the narrative that the 1911 uprising in Guangzhou was led by Sun Yat-sen's Tongmenghui (Revolutionary Alliance). Hence, many loyal supporters of the Nationalist Party make trips to visit the site. During the Japanese occupation, Wang Jingwei, as head of the Nanjing Reformed National Government (a collaborationist regime) made frequent pilgrimages to the site to assert his legitimacy. After World War II, Chiang Kai-shek, also visited the site to signify his regaining control of China. Contemporary politicians in Taiwan who are members of the Nationalist Party also make pilgrimages to the site to show their dedication to the cause of the Republic.

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (rare)

↳

Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳

Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳

Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The site is one of the important historical sites in China and is maintained by the government.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– No

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– Yes

Notes: It is used to educate people of Chinese history.

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

Function for water management:

– No

Part of the transportation network:

– No

Other

–Other [specify]: It is used as a park for residents to enjoy the green scenery.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Yellow Flower Hill (Huanghuagang) 72 Martyrs' Cemetery, Vu, Linh D.. *Governing the Dead: Martyrs, Memories, and Necrocitizenship in Modern China*. Cornell: Cornell University Press, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.7591/cornell/9781501756504.001.0001>.

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